

Devyāmata, vāstuvibhāgalakṣaṇaṣaṣṭisaptimapāṭalaḥ, edition

N f79r, line 4; M f45v, line 1; W f49r, line 2.

- 76.1 tato vibhājayet kṣetraṃ caturaśraṃ susammitam
navadhā cobhayaṃ bhājyaṃ ekāśītipadaṃ śubham
- 76.2 vāstumadhye tato vidvān vāstudevān prakalpayet
ye yasmin te sthitās tasmin brahmādyāḥ śṛṇu sāmpratam
- 76.3 caturaśrīkrte kṣetre nava cobhayakalpite
ekāśītipade brahmā sthito navapadaḥ prabhuḥ
- 76.4 āryamā ca vivasvā ca mitraś ca pṛthivīdharah
prāgādiṣatpadā jñeyā brahmānantarasthitāḥ
- 76.5 savitendras tathā skanda āpavatsaḥ krameṇa tu
āgneyādiṣu koṇeṣu brahmaṇo 'nantare sthitāḥ
- 76.6 sāvitṛī ca jayo rudra āpaś caiva krameṇa tu
yathāpāṭhaṃ krameṇaiva brahmaṇo 'ntaritatāḥ sthitāḥ
- 76.7 vāstumadhye samākhyātā vāstudevās trayodaśa
īśānyādyās tathā cānye vāstumadhye bahiḥ sthitāḥ

Ω = NM(→W)

Verse 7 is missing at MW.

- 1c bhājyaṃ] N; bhājya M 2a vidvān] N; vidvāt M
2b devān] em.; dehān N; de[[ve]]vān M
2c ye] em.; yo N; yau M • te sthitās] conj.; sthitās NM
2d brahmādyāḥ] N; brahmādyā M • sāmpratam] N; śāmpratam M
4a āryamā] N; ācāryamā M 4b pṛthivīdharah] N; pṛthivīdharah M
4d brahmānantara] N; brāhmaṇānanta M
5b āpavatsaḥ] em.; āpavatsāḥ N; āpavatsā M
5d brahmaṇo 'nantare] N; brāhmaṇonantare M 6a sāvitṛī] N; sāvitṛā M
6c pāṭhaṃ] em.; pāṭha NM 6d brahmaṇo 'ntaritatāḥ] N; brāhmaṇontaritatāḥ M
7b devās] em.; devā N 7c īśānyādyās] em.; īśānyādyā N

- 76.8 īso meghādhipaś caiva jayantaś caiva kīrtitaḥ
mahendraś ca tathādityaḥ satyo bhṛśas tathāmbaraḥ N f79v; W f49v
- 76.9 agniś caiva tathā pūṣā vitathaś ca grhakṣataḥ
yamo gandharvo bhr̥ṅgaś ca mṛgākhyāḥ pitaras tathā
- 76.10 dvauvārikaś ca sugrīvaḥ puṣpadantas tataḥ smṛtaḥ
varuṇaś cāsuraḥ śoṣaḥ pāpayakṣmā prakīrtitaḥ
- 76.11 rogaś ca vāsukir mukhyo bhalvāṭaḥ soma eva ca
anantaś cāditiś caiva ditiś caivāmarās tv ime
- 76.12 īśānam āditaḥ kṛtvā dvātriṃśam aparāḥ smṛtaḥ M f46r
jñātavyāḥ sarvayatnena vāstumadhye bahiḥ sthitaḥ
- 76.13 jayanto bhṛśanāmā ca vitatho bhr̥ṅga eva ca
sugrīvaś caiva śoṣaś ca mukhyaś caivāditiḥ kramāt
- 76.14 aṣṭāv ete samākhyātāḥ padadvayabhujō 'marāḥ
śeṣānye 'pi surā jñeyā ekaikapadabhoginaḥ

$\Omega = NM(\rightarrow W)$

8a īso] N; īsā M • meghādhipaś] N; meghādhipāś M 8b jayantaś] N;
yajantaś M • kīrtitaḥ] N; kīrtitaḥ M 8c tathādityaḥ] N; tathādityas M 8d satyo] em.;
satya M; sasatya N • bhṛśas] em.; bhṛśas N; bhṛtyaśas M 9c bhr̥ṅgaś] M; śṛṅgaś N
9b mṛgākhyāḥ] M; mṛṣākhyāḥ N • pitaras] N; [[ci]]pitaras M 10b dantas] N;
danta M 10c śoṣaḥ] em.; śoṣa M; śesaḥ N 11a rogaś] em.; nāgaś NM
• mukhyo] M; mukhye N 11b bhalvāṭaḥ] N; bhalvāṭa M
11c anantaś] M; anant[[ā]]ś N
11cd cāditiś caiva ditiś caivāmarās] M; cāditiścaivāmarās N
12b dvātriṃśam] N; dvātriśa M • aparāḥ] N; padā M
12c jñātavyāḥ] N; jñātavyā M 12d bahiḥ] N; bahi M
13a jayanto] N; yaja M • bhṛśa] em.; bhṛśa M; bṛśa N • nāmā] N; māmā M
14b 'marāḥ]; maro M 14c śeṣānye 'pi] N; śeṣānyapi M

76.15 catasro 'nyās tu bodhavyāś carakādyā bahiḥ sthitāḥ
īśānyādiṣu koṇeṣu na tāsāṃ padakalpanā

76.16 ekāśītipadaṃ vāstu kathitaṃ saviśeṣataḥ
catuḥṣaṣṭipadaṃ bhadre procyate śṛṇu sāmpratam

76.17 caturaśrīkrte kṣetre aṣṭadhobhayabhājite
brahmaṇo 'nantare tasmin koṇarekhāsamanvite

W f50r

76.18 catuḥṣaṣṭipade brahmā sthito madhye catuṣpade
tataḥ samantato jñeyā vāstudevā vyavasthitāḥ

76.19 āryamā dvipado jñeyo vivasvā dvipadas tathā
dvipado mitranāmā ca tathaiva pṛthivīdharāḥ

76.20 brahmaṇo 'nantare dikṣu jñātavyā dvipadā surāḥ
dvau dvau koṇeṣu bodhavyāḥ pādārdhārdhabhujo 'pare

76.21 savitā caiva sāvitṛī indraś caiva jayas tathā
rājanyakṣaś ca rudraś ca āpavatsāpa eva ca

Ω = NM(→W)

15b bahiḥ] N; bahi M

16a ekāśīti] N; ekāśātu M

17a caturaśrī] N; catuśrī M

17c brahmaṇo 'ntare] N; brāhmaṇenantare M1

7d rekhāsamanvite] N; rekhasamanvitaḥ M

18a catuḥ] N; catu M

18c tataḥ samantato] N; tatassamanto M

18d vyavasthitāḥ] N; vyavasthitā M

19a dvipado] N; [[pa]]pado M

20a brahmaṇo 'nantare] N; brāhmaṇenantare M

21c rudraś] em.; rudrāś NM

76.22 parjanyo bhṛśanāmā ca pūṣā ca bhṛṅga eva ca
dvauvāriko 'tha śoṣāś ca rogaś cāditir eva ca

76.23 sārdhārdhapadabhoktāro bahiḥ koṇeṣu samsthitāḥ
śeṣā dvipadabhoktāro jñātavyāḥ ṣoḍaśa kramāt

M f46v

76.24 padabhāgasamuddiṣṭam īśādiyajanam smṛtam
tatheshāsiṣu koṇeṣu carakyādya bahir jayet

76.25 vāstuyāge 'marā ye tu brahmādyāḥ parikīrtitāḥ
mantras teṣāṃ svanāma syād dīpajātiṣu sampuṭāḥ

76.26 ekāśītipadam vāstu catuḥṣaṣṭipadam tathā
dvividham vāstu ākhyātam viśeṣam śṛṇu sāmpratam

W f50v

iti vāstuvibhāgalakṣaṇaṣaṣṭasaptimapāṭalaḥ

Ω = NM(→W)

22a parjanyo] N; parjanyā M • nāmā] N; nānañ M

22c rogaś] em.; nāgaś NM

22d nāgaś cāditir eva ca] conj.; nāgoditirevaca N; nāgoditicarevaca M

23b bahiḥ] N; bahi M 23c śeṣā] M; ś[[o]]eṣā N

23d jñātavyāḥ] N; jñātavyā M 24a samuddiṣṭam] em.; samudiṣṭam NM

24b yajanam] em.; yajana M; jayanam N • smṛtam] M; smṛtaḥ N

24d carakyādya] N; carakādyā M • bahir yajet] N; bahityajet M

25a yāge] N; yājñe M 25b parikīrtitāḥ] N; parikīrtitā M

25c nāma] N; nāma[[to]] M 25cd syād dīpa] N; syādīpa M

25d jātiṣu sampuṭāḥ] N; jātiṣuṣampuṭāḥ M 26b padam] N; padas M

26c vidham] M; viddham N

after 26 iti vāstuvibhāgalakṣaṇaṣaṣṭasaptimapāṭalaḥ] em.;

itidevyāmatevāstuvibhāgalakṣaṇaṣaṣṭasaptimapāṭalaḥ M; itivāstuvibhāgapāṭalaḥ N